

PREDICTION OF MATERIAL BEHAVIOUR OF CLOSED CELL RIGID FOAMS VIA MESOSCOPIC MODELLING

R. Schlimper, M. Rinker and R. Schäuble
Fraunhofer-Institute for Mechanics of Materials (IWM)
Walter-Hülse-Straße 1, 06120 Halle, Germany
ralf.schlimper@iwmh.fraunhofer.de

1 SUMMARY

Deformation and failure behaviour of CFRP foam core sandwich structures was investigated experimentally and numerically. The mechanical properties of the foam were predicted by modelling the foam structure on a mesoscopic scale with a representative volume element (RVE) approach under consideration of the morphological parameters.

Keywords: sandwich structure, representative volume element modelling, foam structure, image analysis, computer tomography

2 INTRODUCTION

To preserve natural resources the energy efficiency of technical processes must be increased. Therefore lightweight structures play an increasing role in broad industrial applications. With their high ratio of bending stiffness and strength to weight sandwich structures are very well suited for high performance lightweight applications in transportation industry [1]. They provide integrated functions like thermal and acoustic insulation which are mainly based on the mesoscopic structure of the foam core material [2]. The investigation of the behaviour of foam materials for application in lightweight sandwich panels has to consider the cell structure of the foam on the mesoscopic scale and the combination of experimental and numerical methods.

Compared to monolithic structures CFRP foam core sandwich structures exhibit a more complex mechanical behaviour due to the combination of various materials [3]. The 4-point-bending-test is an appropriate experimental method for characterizing the deformation and failure behaviour of sandwich panels [4]. While running the tests local damage of the foam occurred already at low-level-loads, which did not destroy the global sandwich structure. With increasing loads the local damage propagated and resulted in the failure of the whole sandwich specimen. Numerical predictions of the sandwich strength have to take into account the described damage progression to provide accurate results. Otherwise prediction of strength based on first local failure would give rise to under-utilisation of the material.

Different approaches are described in literature for the modelling of foam structures on the mesoscopic scale to predict the mechanical properties of the foam from properties of the solid material in the foam and its morphological structure. Among them there are analytical and numerical investigations of unit cells and studies of regular and irregular

multicell models, which can only be calculated numerically, Mills [2] gives an overview about these methods.

The aim of the work presented here is the generation and evaluation of a model which can be used to study the deformation and damage behaviour of the foam and therefore represents the morphological structure of the real foam which influences the mentioned foam behaviour. In a first step the generated model is evaluated by the prediction of the elastic constants of the foam material.

3 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF SANDWICH PANELS

3.1 Materials and Methods

Investigation of stiffness and strength of sandwich panels was carried out on CFRP foam core sandwich specimens. They consist of a PMI (Polymethacrylimide) ROHACELL[®] 51WF foam core and CFRP face sheets each composed of two bindered triax lay ups and an epoxy matrix. They were manufactured by an open mould liquide composite moulding (LCM) technology based on vacuum bagging and resin infusion [5]. The total thickness of the panel was 21,5mm.

Eight specimens were sawn off the panel and subjected to a 4-Point-Bending Test under consideration of ASTM C 393-00. The investigated sandwich panel exhibits high ratios of compression and tension strength of the face sheets to shear strength of the foam core, that is why shear failure of the core is the expected failure mode of the whole panel. Therefore shear deformation was observed via optical strain measurement system ARAMIS which is based on digital image correlation technique.

Finite Element Analysis (FEA) of the 4-Point-Bending Test was carried out. A failure criterion applied to the foam core of the 3-dimensional (3d) model was used to model the fracture behaviour. The criterion was implemented in Postprocessor MSC.Patran using the programming language PCL. An efficiency ratio is calculated by dividing the comparison stress calculated by the criterion and a reference stress potential, it reaches the value 1 if the material theoretically fails.

Figure 1: Experimental setup of 4-Point-Bending Test (left) and ARAMIS shear deformation exposure shortly before specimen failure (right)

3.2 Results of 4-Point Bending Test

As expected on increasing loads the tested sandwich specimens failed under abrupt core shear fracture. The calculated shear strength of the foam core was in good accordance to the manufacturer material specification of 0,81 MPa. The investigation of the failed panels also reveals local compression damages (core crushing) below the load introduction points.

FEA also provides shear stresses between the load introduction point and the supporting point as the dominating loading condition of the foam core. In the region below the load introduction points a multiaxial stress state of compression stresses in thickness direction and longitudinal direction was calculated. The ROHACELL[®]-Failure-Criterion (DKI/Röhlm) [6] shows good results and a conservative prediction of foam failure. The prediction was enhanced by considering residual stresses in the foam core due to the cool down from 180 °C curing temperature to room temperature in the manufacturing process of CFRP foam core sandwich panels. The difference in the thermal expansion coefficients of CFRP and the foam material leads to thermal tension stresses in the foam core, which had to be taken into account for the FEA of experimental tests.

Figure 2: Efficiency ratio of the foam core determined by FEA with the ROHACELL[®]-Failure-Criteria (DKI/Röhlm) without (left) and with (right) temperature load and experimental measured fracture load at 4-Point-Bending test.

FEA shows that local damages below the load introduction points do not cause global failure because of the superposition of thermal tension stresses and compression stresses due to the bending load. The effect of thermal stresses and propagation of local damage strongly depends on the foams mesoscopic structure and can therefore only be accessed by mesoscopic models which cover the morphological parameters of the real foam structure.

4 MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF FOAM STRUCTURE

4.1 Materials and Methods

The investigation of the morphological parameters of the foam structure was carried out on two different types of PMI closed cell rigid foam, ROHACELL[®] 51WF and 71RIST. The properties of the two foam types provided by the manufacturer can be seen on Table 1. Properties of the bulk PMI from which the foam is made were investigated by Chen et al. [7]. Relevant parameters are also listed on Table 1.

Table 1: Properties of investigated PMI foam materials and bulk PMI

	51WF	71RIST	Bulk PMI [7]
foam density [kg/m ³]	52	75	1200
Young's modulus [MPa]	75	105	5200
shear modulus [MPa]	24	42	
Poisson's ratio [-]			0.3*

* added by the author

Specimens of ca. 8x8x15 mm³ were cut off a foam block and investigated via X-ray micro computed tomography (μ CT). Therefore the CT-scanner nanome|x 180NF of the company Phoenix x|ray was used. It has a 180 kV X-ray source and a digital flat panel detector with 512² pixel². The scanning parameters for the acquisition of 1200 projection images were 70 kV, 200 μ A. To reduce computational effort during image analysis the reconstructed volumes were cropped, dimensions and the voxel sizes can be found on Table 2. Figure 3 and 4 show a 3d visualization and slice view of each scanned foam specimen.

Table 2: Dimensions and voxel size of the investigated image data sets

image data	dimensions [voxel ³]	Voxel size [μ m]
51WF	341x361x456	20,06
71RIST	373x356x431	10,65

Figure 3: CT image of ROHACELL[®] 51WF, 3d view (left), slice view (right)

Figure 4: CT image of ROHACELL[®] 71RIST, 3d view (left), slice view (right)

The extraction of the morphological parameters of the foam structure requires several image processing and analysis steps. The necessary algorithms are implemented in the MAVI software [8], which was used here to analyze CT image data of PMI foam. First the 16bit grey value image data had to be separated into material and the surrounding air by setting a threshold in the grey value histogram. The resulting binary image was processed with an Euclidean distance transformation, which provides local extremal values in the center of the foam cells and the watershed transformation for the reconstruction of the foam cells in the 3d image data. For measuring the cell boundaries were deleted via dilation and cells situated on the boundary of the volume image were ignored by object filtering. It provided the morphological parameters of the foam cells, like cell diameter, as the mean value of the chord length measured in 13 directions and cell volume. The diameter of the corresponding ball is calculated from the cell volume for comparison with the generated mesoscopic model (Section 5.2). Visualization of the image processing steps are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Visualization of image processing steps as slice view of the 51WF image data set, binary image after tresholding (left), reconstructed foam cells after watershed transformation (middle), reconstructed foam cells without cell walls (right)

4.2 Results of Image Analysis

Examination of the slices through the volume image data sets showed a very homogeneous mesoscopic structure of the PMI foam. Nearly all cell walls of the observed polyhedral foam cells are flat and of constant thickness. In vertices and struts the solid material accumulates and the thickness increases. The reason for missing cell walls in the binary image (Figure 5) is the thresholding process in the low contrast image data. By human eye the cell walls are completely visible in the image raw data (Figure 3 and 4). Counting the foreground voxels in the binary image of the foam structure provided volume fraction of the solid phase: 0,098 (51WF) and 0,127 (71RIST). Compared to the theoretical values, which were calculated from the foam density and the density of the bulk PMI material: 0.043 (51WF) and 0.0625 (71RIST) they are to high. The difference is mainly caused by artefacts in the volume image. Therefore another scan was carried out of the 51WF specimen with a higher magnification and thus smaller voxel size (10,21 μ m). Analyzing the second image data set led to 0,071. Counting the voxels of the reconstructed cell walls by watershed transformation provided 0,043 which is in very good accordance to the theoretical relative foam density.

The quality of the cell reconstruction process was assessed visibly by adding the system of cell walls of the binary image to the dilated image of the reconstructed cells. The comparison showed good accordance. The mean values of cell sizes extracted from the volume image data sets of both foam types are summarized in Table 3. The statistical distributions of measured cell sizes are shown in Figure 6.

Table 3: Results of image analysis

	51WF		71RIST	
	mean value	std. dev.	mean value	std. dev.
mean cell diameter [mm]	0,99	0,18	0,36	0,05
diameter of corresponding ball [mm]	0,87	0,16	0,31	0,04

Figure 6: Cell size (diameter of corresponding ball) distribution of ROHACELL® 51WF (left) and 71RIST (right) determined from the 3d image data

5 MESOSCOPIC FOAM MODELLING

5.1 Methods

The aim of the mesoscopic modelling of the foam structure is the generation of a model which covers the deformation and damage modes of the real foam. Therefore a geometric model is needed which allows the adjustment of morphological parameters measured in the 3d image data of the foam structure.

The method used in the work presented here is a simplified version of the approach described by Lautensack [9]. It starts with a 3d set of seed points which is generated by an algorithm for random irregular dense packing of equal hard spheres [10]. The sphere diameter is used for adjusting the mean cell diameter of the foam structure. In the next step the Voronoi algorithm is applied to the random set of the seed points by using the Qhull code [11]. It assigns a region to each seed point containing an amount of points which is nearer to the processed seed point than to any other. By doing so it generates a room filling structure of polyhedral cells with flat cell walls, like observed in the 3d image data of the real foam. For comparison with the real foam structure the diameter of the corresponding ball is calculated from the volume of the generated polyhedrons.

The deformation behaviour of the generated representative volume element (RVE) model of the investigated foam structure was analyzed by FEA. Cell walls and struts were meshed with shell and beam elements to cover bending and axial deformation (Figure 8). Thickness of the cell walls was chosen according to the relative density of the real foam structure:

$$\frac{\rho_f}{\rho_s} = \frac{V_s}{V_f} \approx \frac{t \cdot \sum A}{l^3} \quad (1)$$

Where ρ_f and ρ_s are the densities of the foam and the solid material, V_f is the volume of the cubic RVE with the edge length l and V_s is the volume of the solid material, which is mainly composed of the cell walls with the area A and the constant thickness t . The volume fraction of the struts is small and thus neglected in the first step, they are assumed to exhibit the same thickness like the walls and a circular cross section.

For application of multiaxial loading to the RVE, periodic boundary conditions were used as described in [12, 13]. The mean strains of the RVE are expressed in terms of displacement u_i and position X_j of the corresponding nodes of opposite faces A and B:

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_{ij} = \frac{u_i^B - u_i^A}{X_j^B - X_j^A} \quad (2)$$

The required periodic geometric model and finite element mesh were generated as described above. A simple linear elastic material model was assigned to the solid PMI material with the parameters given in Table 1 and a linear analysis was performed to

predict the elastic constants of the PMI foam. The commercial software code ANSYS was used for pre and post processing and the solution of the problem. The stress tensor was calculated from the constraint forces on the bounding faces of the RVE. Young's modulus, shear modulus and Poissons ratio were determined by applying two load cases: First $\varepsilon_{22} \neq 0$ and second $\varepsilon_{12} \neq 0$.

5.2 Results of FE analysis

In a first study the size of the investigated RVE was varied to find out, which size provides good agreement between reliable results on the one hand and minimization of numerical effort on the other. Therefore five models with mean cell size and foam density of ROHACELL[®] 71RIST were calculated in both load cases under varying size of the RVE and thus varying content of foam cells. As expected largest scattering occurred on the results calculated with the smallest RVE, but the scattering of all numerical calculations was generally small. Relative deviations of all models were less than 1%. According to the results the edge length of RVE was defined to be at least 6.5 times the mean cell size and thus containing 800-1000 cells for further numerical calculations.

The results of the prediction of elastic constants of the two investigated foam types are shown in Table 4. In comparison with the parameters provided by the manufacturer (Table 1) it can be seen that the prediction overestimates the stiffness of the investigated foams. In conjunction with the small scattering between the results calculated with five models of one foam type a possible reason for the deviation is the homogeneity of cell sizes in the mesoscopic model. Figure 7 shows the cell size distribution of the mesoscopic models of the two foam types. Compared to the cell size distribution of the real foam, extracted from the 3d images (Figure 6) the variation range of the corresponding ball diameters is almost only one thenth. A wider variation range of cell sizes is expected to reduce the stiffness of the model. The distribution of the solid material between cell walls and struts also effects the stiffness of the mesoscopic foam model. However a calculation with adjusted wall and strut thicknesses, which were measured in SEM image of the foam also did not provide less deviation to the reference values of the elastic constants. For the prediction of accurate material properties the modelling of the real cell size distribution is necessary and has to be taken into account to further investigations.

Table 4: Elastic constants of ROHACELL[®] closed cell rigid foam predicted by FEA

	51WF		71RIST	
	mean value	std. dev.	mean value	std. dev.
Young's modulus [MPa]	81,7	0,1	117,6	0,2
shear modulus [MPa]	31,1	0,1	44,8	0,1
Poisson ratio [-]	0,311	0,001	0,312	0,002

Figure 7: Cell size (diameter of corresponding ball) distribution of the mesoscopic model of ROHACELL[®] 51WF (left) and 71RIST (right)

In addition to the morphological structure the foam density also influences the mechanical properties essentially. Due to the manufacturing process the foam density is subjected to a variation within one foam type. Therefore the relative foam density was varied between $\pm 20\%$ of the reference density provided by the manufacturer in terms of varying thicknesses of the finite elements. The results of calculated Young's moduli are shown in Figure 8. A nearly linear dependency is shown between the Young's modulus and the foam density, it depends on the deformation modes of the walls and the struts, which have to be the topic of further investigations.

Figure 8: FE model of mesoscopic foam structure of ROHACELL[®] 71RIST (left) Young's modulus of ROHACELL[®] 51WF and 71RIST predicted by FEA under varying foam densities (right)

6 CONCLUSION

The deformation and failure of CFRP foam core sandwich panels can be well described by numerical calculations and the application of the ROHACELL[®]-Failure-Criterion especially under consideration of the thermal stresses in the foam core. The material properties of the foam can be predicted by FEA of the deformation of a RVE model of the mesoscopic foam structure, which is adjusted to the cell size measured in

volume image data of the real foam. μ CT and image analysis are appropriate techniques for determination of morphological parameters and their statistical distributions of closed cell rigid polymer foams.

Deviation between predicted material properties and the reference values provided by foam manufacturer were interpreted mainly as a consequence of a less variation range of the cell sizes in the geometric foam model. Models to be used in further investigations of deformation and failure modes of the foam structure have to cover the real cell size distribution measured in the image data. The distribution of solid material between struts and cell walls also effects the deformation behaviour and thus the predicted effective material properties of the foam but can not be measured well in the 3d image data acquired by μ CT. That means several improvements are quite necessary to cover the real foam behaviour.

But increasing use of foam core sandwich structures in high loaded applications requires detailed knowledge of the mechanical behaviour of the foam material. The RVE approach promises high potential to clarify the complex deformation and failure modes.

References

1. D. Zenkert. *Future needs for sandwich structures research and development*, 8th International Conference on Sandwich Structures, Porto, 2008
2. N. Mills. *Polymer Foams Handbook: Engineering and Biomechanics Application and Design Guide*, Butterworth-Heinemann, 2007
3. M. Rinker, T. Hanke and R. Schäuble. *Schädigungs- und Versagensverhalten von hoch belasteten CFK-Schaum-Sandwichstrukturen*, 16. Symposium Verbundwerkstoffe und Werkstoffverbunde, Universität Bremen, Germany, 14-16 March 2007
4. M. Rinker, P. Zahlen and R. Schäuble. *Damage and failure progression in CFRP-foam-sandwich structures*, 8th International Conference on Sandwich Structures, Porto, 2008
5. P. C. Zahlen, M. Rinker and C. Heim, *Advanced Manufacturing of Large, Complex Foam Core Sandwich Panels*, 8th International Conference on Sandwich Structures, Porto, Portugal, May 2008.
6. A. Kraatz, *Anwendung der Invariantentheorie zur Berechnung des dreidimensionalen Versagens- und Kriechverhaltens von geschlossenzelligen Schaumstoffen unter Einbeziehung der Mikrostruktur*, Dissertation Universität Halle, Deutschland, 2007
7. C. P. Chen, W. B. Anderson, and R. S. Lakes. *Relating the Properties of the Foam to the Properties of the Solid from Which it is Made*, Cellular Polymers, 1994, 13, 16-32
8. Fraunhofer ITWM. *MAVI - Modular Algorithms for Volume Images*, 2009. URL <http://www.itwm.fhg.de/mab/projects/MAVI>
9. Lautensack, C. *Random Laguerre Tessellations*, Fakultät für Mathematik der Universität Karlsruhe (TH), 2007

10. M. Bargiel and J. Mościński, *C-language program for the irregular close packing of hard spheres*, Computer Physics Communications, 1991, 64, 183-192
11. C. B. Barber, D. P. Dobkin and H. T. Huhdanpaa, *The Quickhull algorithm for convex hulls*, ACM Trans. on Mathematical Software, 1996, 22(4), 469-483. URL <http://www.qhull.org/>
12. S. Ribeiro-Ayeh, *Finite Element Modeling of the Mechanics of Solid Foam Materials*, School of Engineering Sciences, Kungliga Tekniska Högskolan (KTH), 2005
13. M. Nygard and P. Gudmundson, *Micromechanical modeling of ferritic/pearlitic steels*, Materials Science and Engineering, 2002, A325, 435-443